

THE INTERCULTURAL APPROACHES TO EFL TEACHING AND LEARNING

Nozimaxon G'ofurova

Fergana State university

Gulhayoxon Yigitaliyeva

Fergana State university

Maftuna Turg'unova

Fergana State university

Abstract: The article is devoted to consideration of applying the subject of intercultural aspects in target language for EFL learners to school curriculum. We use data from previous investigations, internet materials and books related to the current theme. In these days, it is known that while learning any foreign languages the impact of cultural and traditional awareness of these languages is broad. In other words, the role of the culture of that nation is vital in learning its language. Not knowing tradition, nation and also culture of target country can cause some verbal problems in this language while speaking and communicational situations. Awareness of culture of country that we are learning its language can also help understanding the world around us. However, in terms of teaching foreign languages with the help of intercultural approaches some teacher restrict themselves in classroom because of the lack of experience in this culture, but they understand that intercultural approaches can be satisfactory aspects for teaching foreign languages to learners. For ESL learners this kind of knowledge is a bit narrow. In these kinds of classrooms students usually speak only their native languages. As a result of this the output skills of their target language can be some problematic and limited ability in this language can be also obstacle for them. The main goal of learning foreign languages should not be communicate not oly with native speakers but also non-native speakers. That is why, learners should learn intercultural approaches.

1. Introduction

The objectives of our research are in two sections; the theoretical section and practical section. Section 1 of this research deals with the theoretical problems of intercultural awareness. There are few foreigners living in Uzbekistan so the majority of us do not need to use languages other than Uzbek language. Many of us need to have use English to learn our concepts . Therefore we have little opportunity to use English. In this section it is explained that why do we have to improve our English. Some of us can have successful life without speaking a single word of English. However for the most of us English is vital in a globalizing world.

In section 2, it is defined that the practical issues of intercultural approaches. Keeping culture in the back of your mind and making sure that you address, maybe not every day, but you making your students more aware of some of the differences that exist, so they can be culturally competent. It is very important that you teach culture in a way that is neutral and professional, and that you do not address it in a way that is, some about agreement. It is not about trying to make any kinds of arguments this way or that way. We want to make sure that we tell our adult students, because they are able to understand that the reason we are having this discussion about whatever cultural element, is because you want them to be successful in communication from that culture. At least in my case, that is what has helped me in dealing with sometimes those little difficult topics that deal cultural differences. It is exiting topic, and your student will enjoy it.

2. Methodology

Intercultural Approaches to EFL Teaching aims at bringing into light the importance of two areas in foreign languages teaching and learning. Intercultural Approaches is interested in all levels of English language education (middle, secondary, and tertiary) and encourages the submission of various types of contributions: empirical studies (complete or in progress), state of the art papers (comprehensive, systematic reviews with implications for EFL classroom), and creatively devised activities for intercultural instruction (showing their theoretical foundation and implementation procedure). The future teacher must know and understand about intercultural encoders. When they teach the international class and they do not know what is either cultural encoders it can be a lot of conflict and misunderstanding. It is important to understand the intercultural encounters because international class have a lot of different cultures. It is needed to avoid misunderstanding or conflict. As we know before different culture it means different interpretation. Speaking in a language properly is not enough. Our teachers told us all about grammar, vocabulary and use of greetings, but this cannot help us understand that culture is embedded in language. This is integral because learning languages is a great way to learn to respect cultures that are different to your own. However, this does not develop naturally as we can see in a discrimination towards people who are different.

3 The importance of culture in teaching EFL learner

A lot of people think about the clothing, food, festivals, or music of a certain country is culture. This is called surface or visible culture. Studying surface can be very interesting and motivating to students, but they also need to learn about deep culture to be able to effectively communicate with people from different cultures. People often discuss the difference between deep culture and surface culture by using the metaphor of an iceberg. An iceberg is a floating mass of ice. The visible part of the iceberg

represents the surface aspects of culture like dress, art, and music. The part of the iceberg that is underwater represents the less visible aspects of culture, aspects like humor, communication patterns, and respect for authority. Despite the fact that these aspects of culture are invisible, they are the bigger source of cultural difference and the bigger impact on people's day-to-day life. A good starting point is to have students create their own cultural iceberg. For that activity teacher should ask students to list elements of their own culture for each level. At surface level, they might list foods and holiday traditions, while at the deepest level, students might list values and attitudes related to friendship and familial patterns. As students develop their own cultural awareness, teacher might have them return their cultural icebergs to continue adding to them. The cultural activity iceberg activity is a good place to begin because it helps students explore their own culture. We should always start with what is familiar to students, so it is best to start with activities focused on your students' own cultural awareness. Then teacher can move on activities focused on students' communities and on global cultures. The "What is Weird" activity helps students think critically about their own culture. For this activity, find a guidebook about your country, in print or online, and have students read the section where the author explains your local culture. It can be really eye-opening for students to think about a newcomers perspective on their culture. A possible source is Wikitravel.org, an open-source with information for travelers. A follow-up activity could be for students to develop a brochure or website explaining aspects of their local culture to visitors or newcomers.

4 Delivering new perspective in classroom in terms of teaching foreign languages via intercultural approaches

Since the 1980s linguists and other scholars in the West have ever caded the importance of enhancing students intercultural communication competence in foreign language education. The intercultural communication perspective is a new for EFL learners in Uzbekistan and its implementation and evaluation is still under development. So far the ever case of trends in EFL have focused almost exclusively on classroom based courses. However, in order to catch with the main trend of foreign language education there is also a need to implement the course cultural dimension into distant cautions institutions.

In order to practice our investigation two classes had to be observed in terms of current topic. In this observation questionnaire was utilized from data collecting tools. Two classroom, in Fergana, in 9th grade from a private school were choosen which has the subject of intercultural awareness in its' school curriculum and public schools which has not this subject. The students should choose one answer from three options. They are *Yes*, *Sometimes*, *No*. Before beginning the observation 4 essential tips are needed for it. The first one is starting with a plan. The second one is observe, the next one is document the classroom observations and reflect. Before beginning the

investigation some questionnaire were searched from the internet sources and collected about how to design questionnaire.

Questionnaire about the culture:

1. *Are you interested in western culture?*
2. *Are you interested in traditional American culture?*
3. *Do you make comparison between western culture and traditional American culture.*
4. *Do you compare the different meaning of the same subject in terms of western and American culture?*
5. *Are you confused with some western cultural factors while reading English books?*
6. *Do you pay attention to cultural connotation while meeting new words?*
7. *Does your English teacher introduce related culture background to you before the study of the text?*
8. *Does your English teacher explain the words' cultural meaning to you when teaching vocabulary?*

5 Results

The general result is really negative in public school in terms of world culture. If we pay attention the first and the second question 60% and 47% of students do not interest western and American cultures. This is because, teachers do not get students interested in culture through language. To the next questions 86% and 100% of students gave no answer. This is very negative result. Because, students cannot pay attention to cultural things while reading texts. To fifth and sixth questions 83% and 33% of students said yes. Therefore, they really need cultural education. In the last two questions the real problem is focused, and also solution can be shown for us.

The next questionnaire was given to private school students in 9th grade (they are also 30). The results of the questionnaire here is very controversial. This is the effect of the subject of intercultural awareness in the private school.

6 Conclusion

To conclude, in these days teaching and learning English languages cannot be reduced, and should be taught as important subjects of linguistics like morphology, phonology and vocabulary. When it comes to teaching culture theoreticians restrict themselves to learn a culture. In the classroom of English as a second language (ESL) this is not a problem at all, but for learners of English as a foreign language (EFL) this is a narrow view. In EFL classroom, all students may be monolingual and study foreign cultures in their native country. They have limited knowledge about target culture, as a result of this being culturally competent students is can be a bit difficult for them. Their aim to learning language for not only communicating with native speakers but also non-native speakers in English. This is because they are International language

learners. They have to be a culturally competent all over the world in order to communicate in each field such as technology, business, tourism and entertainment. In other words, in culturally diverse environment our students should learn cultural knowledge.

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